

Titanium Salts of Organic Acids

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Titanium salts of organic acids have been prepared by the action of titanium tetrabromide on organic acids; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

Funk and Rogler¹ prepared $Ti(OPh)_4$, $PhOH$ and $TiCl_2(C_{10}H_7O)_2$ by heating $TiCl_4$ with phenol and naphthol respectively in CS_2 . I. G. Eerbenind² prepared alcoholate and phenylate of titanium by heating $TiCl_4$ and aromatic hydroxy compounds with organic hydroxy compounds in presence of organic bases. Levy³ prepared titanium tetraphthalate, α -naphthol titanate, and picryl titanate by the action of $TiCl_4$ on respective phenols in benzene. Prasad and Tripathi⁴ prepared a number of phenyl and nitrophenyl titanates by the action of $TiBr_4$ on the corresponding phenols and nitrophenols respectively.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of titanium salts of some organic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

The organic acids used were of Merck's or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality. Titanium tetrabromide was prepared by the method of Olsen and Ryan⁵. It was then extracted with anhydrous ether, distilled over metallic sodium.

General Procedure.—The organic acid was added in excess to an ethereal solution of titanium tetrabromide. The mixture was slowly heated in an oil bath to remove ether and the temperature was then raised and maintained at 10° to 15° above the melting points of the respective acids. When the evolution of HBr had ceased, the flask was cooled. The mixture was taken out, washed with anhydrous ether or absolute ethanol repeatedly till free of acids, and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Titanium was estimated as TiO_2 .

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, fairly stable in dry atmosphere and are generally insoluble in common organic solvents. These are decomposed on boiling with water or dilute alkalis.

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1944, 252, 323.
2. *A. G. Fr.*, Sept. 29, 1937, 818,570.
3. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1893, vi, 25, 533.
4. *This Journal*, 1958, 35, 177.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2215.

TABLE I

Organic acids.	Compounds formed.	Colour.	M.P.	%Titanium.	
				Found.	Reqd.
Lauric	Ti [CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₀ COO] ₄	Dirty brown	57°	5.56	5.88
Myristic	Ti [CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂ COO] ₄	Yellow	79°	5.03	5.02
Palmitic	Ti [CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₄ COO] ₄	Dirty white	97°	4.49	4.49
Stearic	Ti [CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₆ COO] ₄	Light brown	77°	4.07	4.05
Cinnamic	Ti (C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH.COO) ₄	Dirty orange	*145°	7.51	7.54
Benzoic	Ti (C ₆ H ₅ COO) ₄	Ash	115°	8.03	9.00
Adipic	Ti [(CH ₂) ₄ (COO) ₂] ₂	..	152°	14.21	14.20
Salicylic	Ti [C ₆ H ₄ $\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \text{<} \\ \text{COO} \end{matrix}$] ₂	Grey	..	14.36	15.00
Succinic	Ti [(CH ₂) ₂ (COO) ₂] ₂	White	*160°	16.76	17.14
Malic	Ti [CH ₂ -COO CH(OH).COO] ₂	Pale yellow	158°	15.33	15.38
Camphoric	Ti [C ₈ H ₁₄ (COO) ₂] ₂	Dark brown	*163°	10.76	10.81
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	Ti [(NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ .COO) ₂] ₂	Pale yellow	*128°	6.68	6.74
3, 5-Dinitrosalicylic	Ti [(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ $\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \text{<} \\ \text{COO} \end{matrix}$] ₂	Brown	..	9.65	9.60

*Denotes decomposition temperature.

The results in Table I show that only the carboxylic group is affected in all the cases studied, excepting salicylic acid, and the normal salts of titanium are formed.

One molecule of TiBr₄ combines with four molecules of a monobasic acid and two molecules of a dibasic acid with the formation of normal salts of titanium. In the case of salicylic acid, however, H of OH group is also replaced.

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